

RESPONSE PAPER

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PROGRAM CODE: DDIA

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

THE ART OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

An academic writing is rarely taught as a self-standing course in our, Ethiopian, educational system. As a result, many students struggle with writing and the difficult feelings, particularly the lack of confidence, that writing stirs up. This being the case, the course on “the Art of Academic Writing” has allowed me the opportunity to understand and practice academic writing skills that are central and will be the foundation of my doctoral studies with EUCLID. The course material is organized fairly well and explains the writing process from start to finish. It can easily engage students in writing at a graduate level and can help them develop the research, composition, and argument skills they need to succeed in graduate programs. This course will be particularly useful for students like me who have not studied at an international university or who are returning to university after a quite long period in public service. I have learned the key stages in the academic writing process, how to construct compelling paragraphs, including introductions and conclusions, how to read and write critically, and how to make effective use of citation styles while referring others’ work.

2) THE WAY THE COURSE MATERIAL IS STRUCTURED

The course pack, “International Academic Writing,” is divided into different sections or segments, which contain concepts, terminologies, explanations and examples for self-study. However, I do not see as such any logical order or transition from one section to another. But still it is designed in a way it can equip students with the theory

and practice of academic writing, from planning to style. It is particularly important for students like me who study English as a second language. The first segment of the package consists of the basics of essay writing, which covers issues like characteristics of good essay; basic steps in essay writing; researching the essay topic; organizing ideas; and writing, referencing, and editing the essay. The second segment of the course pack is about academic paper and different issues related to paper, where the discussions on plagiarism and citation are given due attention. The course material also includes sections on rules of thumb for writing papers, important reminders, style guide, basic differences and influences of change in American and British English, sample corrections to papers, CMC Crib Sheet, and Latin Abbreviations and Expressions. Structure wise the course pack, being a combination of materials from different sources, proceeds from one section to another without any proper transition. However, this in no way undermines the relevance of the material.

3) ESSAY WRITING AND STYLES

As mentioned earlier, the course pack gives an overall picture of academic writing. In doing so, it starts with the basics of writing an essay where it shows the main steps to follow. It also guides how to organize ideas and emphasizes the need for creative and critical thinking. The two thinking approaches have their objective; creative thinking mainly helps the broadening of ideas whereas critical thinking allows narrowing the focus of ideas. Moreover, I found the notion of “balancing” very important. Essays, being balanced, should capture different perspectives from different authors that reflect different arguments on a particular topic (EUCLID 2015, 39).

When it comes to actual writing, structuring the essay in a way it can effectively communicate the ideas of the writer and also answering the questions the essay tries to address is the first important thing. Any typical essay has three main structures: introduction, body, and conclusion. Normally, I consider the introduction and conclusion as the frames for my paper or any academic writing.

The issue of plagiarism has got the proper place in the course material. The course material stipulates what plagiarism is and how it affects the reputation of writers. It emphasizes that all academic writings require us to cite all the sources we have used in the preparation of our work. Clear referencing allows readers to learn about the wider literature through one’s writings. Otherwise, it is a misrepresentation of others’ work and can result in serious academic offense with possible serious consequences (EUCLID 2015, 12).

In this regard, one of the challenges I have been facing mostly in academic writing has been to successfully fit in my ideas with material from different sources. Particularly, getting that point of “balance” has been a real challenge. I found the course pack very important in indicating the ways to ease this burden, through appropriate citation. I have learned techniques that I can use to introduce quoted and paraphrased material effectively in my academic writings. Honestly, I also found the topic on “When

NOT to Cite” as equally relevant as the one on when and how to cite. Here, it is also worth stating that the uniformity of citation is very important.

Talking about style and citation, the distinction between personal and academic styles has been given much attention. Academic style refers to using logical connectors so that there is flow in the writing (EUCLID 2015, 39). The course material further recognizes style is not something that has one standard definition and every writer understands the same way. Correspondingly, I would have been more comfortable to see the course material showing techniques of ensuring the balance between personal and academic style, if at all this is required and possible. However, the material fails not only to explicitly and unequivocally define what “balance” of style is but also how it can be achieved. It has concentrated principally on the applications of headings and connectors. Furthermore, it somehow overlooks to exhaustively discuss the different variants of styles that are widely used, including the American Psychological Association (APA), the Modern Language Association of America (MLA) and the Modern Humanities Research Association (MHRA).

On the other hand, I am comfortable knowing that EUCLID prefers the Chicago Rules (Turabian) as a style guide which is a style I have been somewhat familiar with. “The CMS crib sheet” guides and also incorporates important concepts and applications concerning style. On the contrary, the choice between American and British English is quite difficult for me as I have been using both without any appropriate distinction. For the most part, I could not easily catch the different pronunciation of words in American and British English although they have the same spelling or vice-versa. This will be one of the areas I will be working hard and I am thankful to EUCLID to provide me with such a concise and illustrative material on the subject.

Until I read this material, I wrongly thought Chicago and Turabian styles are different. From the material, I cleared this misunderstanding and further understood two variants of the Chicago/Turabian style, Author-Date, and Notes-Bibliography, which can be applied in academic referencing. The first method uses footnotes or endnotes to place citations at the bottom of a page or the end of a paper; these notes refer to the sources that are further detailed in the paper’s final bibliography. The second method uses in-text, parenthetical references that correspond to a final “Reference List” (EUCLID 2015, 66).

Normally, bibliographies list the materials referred and can help readers to use the same for further researching and referencing. I must confess that one thing which has always been confusing me was “do bibliographies include sources that we have not directly referred to in our written work even if they were somehow valuable to the writing?” I am now aware this is very important and hence need to be incorporated in the list.

4) CONCLUSION

Academic writing is a process that goes through many stages. The course material, in addition to giving me insight on what academic writing is, helped me to

acquaint myself with other aspects of writing conventions, including punctuation, the use of connectors, paragraph, and essay format. Most of the lessons from this course are applicable immediately and also will be the basis for my future studies in other courses. Most of all, I understood academic writing requires the use of an appropriate style that differs in significant ways from other forms of written communication. Using an academic writing style is not just about choosing the right words; it is about setting out ideas and arguments in a coherent, accessible and well-evidenced manner. This means that when learning to write in an academic context, one must identify the conventions of academic writing through exposure and analysis, through practice applying those conventions, and through feedback from peers and instructors.

To sum up, I found the course material, particularly being an introductory course for graduate students, comprehensive and serving its purpose very well. Generally, I consider this course pack as a practical guide and one that lays the foundation for future courses in this program. The essential questions and the associated answers coupled with the sample corrections to papers give practical and first-hand guidance to students. This in mind, I will keep it accessible as a reference to consult while I will be writing the different papers in the course of my Ph.D. study.

REFERENCES

Euclid University. 2020. ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1. <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/CUEsEiHd7B/ACA-401%20Coursepack.pdf> (accessed February 21, 2020).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.